

VERBAL AGGRESSION AS A SPECIAL TYPE OF COMMUNICATIVE TACTIC

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Abstract

In our work below, verbal aggression is considered as a communicative-pragmatic phenomenon, its differences from related concepts are revealed, and the concepts of direct and indirect verbal aggressive actions are introduced. In addition, a classification of the methods of manifestation of aggression is proposed from the point of view of the theory of speech acts.

Keywords: speech aggression, speech act, pragmalinguistics, psycholinguistics

The study of aggression is currently carried out within the following humanities: psychology, sociology, philosophy, cultural studies and linguistics. Aggression is primarily a psychological phenomenon, so its essence is studied in depth in psychology. In linguistics, the study of aggression as a phenomenon of speech communication began relatively recently, and therefore the phenomenon of verbal aggression has not yet been sufficiently studied. Among linguists dealing with this problem, there is no unity in understanding the nature of aggression in speech, as well as in choosing a term that represents it. As Yu.V noted, words such as verbal aggression, verbal aggression, and linguistic aggression are widely used. According to Shcherbinina, the complexity of defining the concept of "speech aggression" is, first of all, that this phenomenon cannot be considered as the only form of behavior that reflects any motivation. This term is applied to various speech acts, motivation, cases of manifestation, forms of verbal symbols, intentional orientation, and therefore is fully understood through generalized concepts such as "pathogenic communication", "negative" speech. cannot be riffled. influence", "roughness of speech", etc. [1. p. 14].

For all disciplines dealing with this problem, the most general and frequently used definition of aggression is defined as follows: aggression is any action aimed at harming an object. Often verbal aggression refers to similar non-aggressive verbal responses. Often the words "aggression" and "conflict" are synonymous. However, we tend to agree with NE. According to Shchurkova, "modern ethics tends to interpret the category of conflict higher: it is a contradiction that has arisen in the process of growth and development of moral relations, and its resolution is a step forward ... Conflicts and disagreements. immediate elimination and It is necessary to prevent conflicts that help to accelerate moral growth In addition, the concept of conflict is much broader than the concept of aggression. As Yu. V. noted, "... conflict is not verbal aggression, and verbal aggression is not a conflict, rather, it is one of the non-constructive ways of solving it" [1 . page 18] "Oh, infection!"- we exclaim, for example, when we feel a sharp pain. On the surface, this statement seems aggressive. Such a verbal reaction according to AR Luria, such a statement is not a "speech statement in the true sense of the word", it "has the nature of voluntary or previously reinforced vocal or speech reactions" [2.

page 188]. Yu.V. Shcherbinina calls such statements spontaneous verbal reactions to stress. page 18] and VI Gelvis uses the term "stress invective" [3. page 45]. In the studies of some linguists, the concept of verbal aggression is equated with the concept of invective (VIJelvis, TIBarsukova). However, by invective we mean the use of profanity, curses and aggression, which in most cases can be expressed without using them. That is, invective can be considered only a special case of aggression. Also, using invective is not necessarily offensive. As LI pointed out. According to Skvortsov, "swearing has a communication function" [4. Page 54]:Great, Vaska! How long have you been gone, bastard! so how are you (from a daily conversation). As you can see from the context, the word "naughty" in this example does not indicate aggression, it indicates the level of familiarity between the addresser and addressee, as well as the style of conversation. In psychology, verbal aggression is considered as an expression of negative feelings towards someone or something. However, we tend to agree with TA. Vorontsova "from the point of view of communicative linguistics, it is important not only what he said, but why he said it" [5. S. 4]. In this regard, in order to study the essence of verbal aggression in depth, it is necessary to consider it from the point of view of two disciplines: psycholinguistics and pragmalinguistics. Psycholinguistics is a field of linguistics that primarily studies the phenomenon of the psyche [6. S. 1]. selects linguistic units based on extralinguistic factors such as culture, character, and situation. The focus of psycholinguistics includes "the representation of the human world as a verbal communication activity". If we consider an aggressive action through the prism of the psycholinguistic theory of activity (AALeontiev, ANLeontiev), we define it as "transition, as a result of which external processes in the form... becomes the processes that take place in the psyche. plane, on the plane of consciousness; at the same time, they undergo a specific transformation - they are generalized, verbalized, reduced and, most importantly, able to develop further..." [8. page 149]. In other words, reactions to negative stimuli become verbal and mental activities. For example, the reaction to a clear rejecting attitude can be an insult, expressed in an aggressive form, including a threat, anger: You bastards! ...I'll also show you where the crayfish winter!(from a daily interview). Pragmalinguistics is one of the directions of pragmatics, the object of its study is the relationship between language units and the conditions of their use in a certain communicative space, the place of speech interaction to describe it and showing the time is important. speaker and listener, their goals and expectations" [9. P. 12]. From the point of view of pragmalinguistics, the purpose of verbal aggression is "the desire to change the flow of the communication process in the direction desired by the addressee by attacking the "communicative rights" of the speech partner" [5. P. 7]. Some researchers dealing with the problem of aggression have tried to systematize and classify the manifestation of this concept, in particular, in oral speech. The first such attempts were made by psychologists. A. Bass in 1976 proposed 4 types of verbal aggression: 1. Verbal active direct (ie indirect) means of verbally insulting or humiliating the recipient):...Ugly, vile! Abominable, depraved creature! (AP Chekhov. Chorus Girl). 2. Verbal active indirect (distributing gossip about the third person):Yes, he is stupid, because of everyone... known(from daily conversation). 3. Verbal passive direct (refusal to speak with advertisement) resat: -Are you eating? -... - Why don't you keep quiet, I'm talking to you (from a daily conversation). In this case, the addressee is deliberately silent in order to show his aggressive mood towards the addressee: the addressee does not deserve a response. spring explanations) [10. page 29]. Although this classification does not cover all manifestations of verbal aggression, it has a certain value and

is used as a basis for building other classifications. Linguists classify aggression according to the forms of manifestation. Yu.V. Shcherbinin, LM Semenyuk, M.Yu. Fedosyuk, TV Shmeleva, based on the concept of speech genre, identifies the forms of verbal aggression, insult, threat, rude demand, etc. (12 in total) and explains it by "the study of verbal aggression.

"From the point of view of the theory of speech genres, it expands the range of aspects of research, which allows us to consider not only purposeful, active speech aggression, but also behavior, mediation." page 152]. In our research, we consider the manifestation of verbal aggression in interpersonal communication. Interpersonal communication involves the exchange of messages and their interpretation by two or more people in contact with each other. A communication unit is a speech act. Based on this, and taking into account that pragmatics is often combined with the theory of speech communication, or in other words, the theory of speech acts, we consider it appropriate to classify verbal aggression according to its forms. manifestation from the concept of speech act. A speech act is "the minimum basic unit of speech communication, in which one communicative goal of the speaker is realized and affects the receiver" [11. page 57].

Based on the above, we defined the concept of verbally aggressive act as a speech act that includes the verbally expressed aggression of the speaker directed at the addressee or a third person. It is known that "the meaning of the utterance can be drastically different from the meaning of the same sentence in relation to a certain speech situation" [12. B. 290]. In this regard, we distinguish direct and indirect verbal aggressive actions. In direct verbal aggressive actions, "the illocutionary goal of the speaker is directly manifested" [13], i.e. the addressee openly insults, threatens, etc. If aggression is presented indirectly (indirectly, hidden) in speech, we talk about indirect verbal aggressive actions. Analysis of examples of aggression in everyday speech and fiction shows us that almost all verbal aggressive actions discussed below depend on internal verbal filling. 'led to the idea that it can be direct and indirect (except for the ironic speech act). , which is always hidden). Based on the classification of Yu.V. Specifically, we identified the following verbally aggressive behaviors (VA): VA insults, VA hostile words, VA threats, VA rude demands, VA rude rejections, VA reprimands (expressions), VA accusations, AND sarcasm. In the table, we have given examples of direct and indirect verbal aggressive actions (PVA and KVA).

Let's give some explanations . An insult is any word or phrase that contains an offensive characteristic of the addressee. A. Vejbitskaya defines the insult formula as "You are Khsan". The pronoun "you" can be omitted and the "X" represents a real insult. When insulted, "communicative pressure on a person occurs by influencing his value framework" [12. P. 12], i.e. With the help of a verbally aggressive act of insult, the addressee gains a dominant position. Defensive insult is a reaction to a previous manifestation of aggression. From a psychological point of view, a person who uses defensive insults experiences an explosion of negative feelings (emotional catharsis). In the example given in the table, the refusal to give money, as well as explaining the reason for this with the help of an insult "unlucky spender", causes a flow of negative emotions in the interlocutor, which he expresses in the form of insults in response. Intentional insult is a purposefully directed aggression, further humiliating the addressee girl , purposely chooses words to instill an inferiority complex about his height (thickness, compass). is heard because... Does not contain invective or rude direct statements, but forces the recipient to open the implication: You are smart! Lukashenko is not smart, so you are stupid.

Hostile attitude is an expression of negative attitude towards people. One of the methods of such reasoning is "nitpicking": "the speaker finds fault in some moments of the addressee's speech - unsuccessful formulas, speech errors, not very convincing examples, etc." [1. page 164]. Enmity can also be expressed in the form of malice or curse, which is almost the same thing and differs only in the presence of the action verb "to curse" in the VA of curse. The VA of the word enmity is shown through indirect comparison and allusion. For comparison, aggression is manifested by comparing the addressee or something related to him with an object, subject, property that is offensive to him (for example, a comparison with a cow). The VA of the tip can be understood by guessing. Usually the assumption is very simple because the advice is transparent. Threat (menasiv) - the intention to cause physical, material or any other harm to the receiver. Threat VA often corresponds to the design If..., This..., where in the first part the addressee defines the conditions, if not fulfilled, the addressee is in danger of something (in the second part): If you are not present, I will kill you if you give the letter! This situation E.g. , the return of the letter, in which the sender threatens to kill the recipient if it is not fulfilled. There are many indirect ways of expressing VA threat. Such threats do not contain clear information about the consequences for the receiver (Now what will I do with you...), the threat can be expressed using intonation and hostile gestures: If Some people do not stop immediately, others are very 'it's going to hurt!= If you don't stop now, you're going to hurt. A rude demand is usually manifested in the speaker's desire to get rid of the interlocutor or force him to perform some action (Get out of here!). Implicit rough demand is less commonly used, it is called demand. Rude refusal - a rude, impolite refusal of a request, demand, etc.- Buy me this toy! - You're in charge!= I'm not buying it. Blame and blame should be considered conditional verbal aggressive actions, because every reprimand, like a reprimand, is not expressed in an aggressive form. Accusation, on the other hand, is always aggressive. Irony lies in the conflict between the literal and the hidden meaning. To sum up, of course, irony is not always an expression of aggression, but cases of using sarcastic speech act as a hidden expression of negative aggressive feelings are frequent. Irony AND allows the speaker to express his or her reaction to what is happening without words:Return Congratulations on your excellent essay. = Your writing is disgusting.

Thus, we tried to analyze the essence of aggression from the point of view of psycholinguistics and pragmalinguistics and to classify the ways of its manifestation from the point of view of the theory of speech acts.

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